

CRISES AND TOURISM: AN EARLY ASSESSMENT ON THE RUSSIA-UKRAINE WAR

Burak Atasoy*, Hasan Önal Şeyhanlioğlu** & Burhanettin Zengin***

Abstract

This research compares the Russia-Ukraine crisis with previous global crises and provides a quick assessment of the initial effects of the crisis on tourism. In addition, it is evaluated how the crisis has shaped international societies, economies and tourism. Since the crisis is very new, and due to the absence of deeper data, the authors made a systematic review. In this context, newspapers, journals, scientific publications and reports were examined. Global tourism is in a serious contraction due to the crisis. The interruption of international trade, the global food crisis and the increase in oil prices have restricted the global tourism and travel industry, especially food and beverage, accommodation and transportation. Emerging problems such as poverty, hunger, insufficient supply, inflationary pressure, closure of supply chains and loss of workforce require the UN to reconsider its sustainable development goals. The war between Russia and Ukraine has been criticized for all kinds of negative effects such as life and property security. The contribution of international non-governmental organizations to the solution of crises such as food, oil and supply chain is seen as insufficient. Previous research on tourism and crisis literature mentions the effects of past crises on tourism. This research contributes to the literature on the Russia-Ukraine crisis in two ways: First, it deals with the crisis arising from the war both in terms of previous global crises and in terms of sub-branches of tourism and secondly it analyzes how the crisis will play a role on future tourism. This study contributes to the area because it is one of the first researches to report the effects on global tourism by providing an early assessment of the crisis.

Keywords: Russia – Ukraine War; Tourism; Tourism Crisis.

CRISES E TURISMO: UMA AVALIAÇÃO ANTIGA DA GUERRA RÚSSIA-UCRÂNIA**Resumo**

Esta pesquisa compara a crise Rússia-Ucrânia com crises globais anteriores e fornece uma avaliação rápida dos efeitos iniciais da crise no turismo. Além disso, avalia-se como a crise moldou as sociedades internacionais, as economias e o turismo. Como a crise é muito nova, e devido a ausência e dados mais aprofundados, os autores fizeram uma revisão sistemática. Nesse contexto, foram examinados jornais, revistas, publicações científicas e relatórios. O turismo global está em séria contração devido à crise. A interrupção do comércio internacional, a crise global de alimentos e o aumento dos preços do petróleo restringiram a indústria global de turismo e viagens, especialmente alimentos e bebidas, hospedagem e transporte. Problemas emergentes como pobreza, fome, oferta insuficiente, pressão inflacionária, fechamento de cadeias de abastecimento e perda de força de trabalho exigem que a ONU reconsidere suas metas de desenvolvimento sustentável. A guerra entre a Rússia e a Ucrânia foi criticada por todos os tipos de efeitos negativos, como a vida e a segurança da propriedade. A contribuição das organizações não governamentais internacionais para a solução de crises como a alimentar, petrolífera e da cadeia de abastecimento é vista como insuficiente. Pesquisas anteriores sobre turismo e literatura de crise mencionam os efeitos de crises passadas sobre o turismo. Esta pesquisa contribui para a literatura sobre a crise Rússia-Ucrânia de duas maneiras: primeiro, trata da crise decorrente da guerra tanto em termos de crises globais anteriores quanto em termos de sub-ramos do turismo e, em segundo lugar, analisa como a crise desempenhará um papel no turismo futuro. Este estudo contribui para a área ao ser um dos primeiros a relatar os efeitos no turismo global, fornecendo uma avaliação inicial da crise.

Palavras-chave: Guerra Rússia-Ucrânia; Turismo; Crise do turismo.

CRISIS Y TURISMO: UNA EVALUACIÓN TEMPRANA DE LA GUERRA RUSIA-UCRANIA**Resumen**

Esta investigación compara la crisis Rusia-Ucrania con crisis mundiales anteriores y proporciona una evaluación rápida de los efectos iniciales de la crisis en el turismo. Además, se evalúa cómo la crisis ha moldeado las sociedades, las economías y el turismo internacionales. Dado que la crisis es muy nueva, los autores realizaron una revisión sistemática. En este contexto, se examinaron periódicos, revistas, publicaciones científicas e informes. El turismo mundial se encuentra en una grave contracción debido a la crisis. La interrupción del comercio internacional, la crisis alimentaria mundial y el aumento de los precios del petróleo han restringido la industria mundial del turismo y los viajes, especialmente de alimentos y bebidas, alojamiento y transporte. Los problemas emergentes como la pobreza, el hambre, el suministro insuficiente, la presión inflacionaria, el cierre de las cadenas de suministro y la pérdida de mano de obra requieren que la ONU reconsidere sus objetivos de desarrollo sostenible. La guerra entre Rusia y Ucrania ha sido criticada por todo tipo de efectos negativos, como la seguridad de la vida y la propiedad. La contribución de las organizaciones no gubernamentales internacionales a la solución de crisis como la alimentaria, la petrolera y la cadena de suministro se considera insuficiente. Investigaciones previas sobre turismo y literatura sobre crisis mencionan los efectos de crisis pasadas en el turismo. Esta investigación contribuye a la literatura sobre la crisis Rusia-Ucrania de dos maneras: en primer lugar, aborda la crisis derivada de la guerra tanto en términos de crisis globales anteriores como en términos de subramas del turismo y, en segundo lugar, analiza cómo la crisis desempeñará un papel en el futuro del turismo. Es la primera investigación que informa los efectos sobre el turismo mundial al proporcionar una evaluación temprana de la crisis.

Palabras clave: Guerra Rusia-Ucrania; Turismo; Crisis turística.

Licenciada por Creative Commons
4.0 / Internacional
CC BY 4.0

* PhD in tourism management (2022) from Sakarya University of Applied Sciences. He received master's (2019) and a bachelor's degree (2016) from Erciyes University. His scientific fields of study include tourism sociology, tourism marketing and tourist behavior. The author has articles published in various scientific journals and papers presented at international conferences. ORCID: 0000-0002-9742-8112, e-mail: burakatasoy@subu.edu.tr

** PhD at Sakarya University of Applied Sciences, Department of Tourism Management (2022). Master's degree from Muğla University, Department of Business Administration (2018). Graduated from Muğla University, School of Tourism and Hotel Management, Department of Hospitality Management (2015). Professor Assistant study at Batman University Tourism Faculty at the Department Tourism Management. His main fields of study are tourism management, food and beverage management and management psychology. ORCID: 0000-0002-9056-5237, e-mail: hseyhanlioglu93@gmail.com (Corresponding author).

*** Ph.D. in Tourism Management (1994) from Istanbul University. He is a professor at the Department of Tourism Guidance at Sakarya University of Applied Sciences. His research interests accounting, tourism and marketing. ORCID: 0000-0002-6368-0969, e-mail: bzengin@subu.edu.tr

1 INTRODUCTION

Disasters and crises are unexpected, rapidly developing and producing severe effects (Scott & Laws, 2006). Tourism is one of the most vulnerable industries to disasters and crises, and public administration primarily examines the tourism industry in the face of crises (Carlsen and Liburd, 2008). It is a structure affected by tourism crises. Any attack or crime negatively affects the perspective of that destination (Navarrete, and Velasco Ávalos, 2020). From the beginning of the century to the present, there have been many crises such as terrorism, nature, epidemics and the economy.

These have weakened the growth of tourism on a local, regional and global scale and led to its decline (Henderson, 2007). The Gulf war, SARS, the 9/11 New York attacks, the 2007-08 economic depression and the 2013 Ebola epidemic are the main crises that have damaged the tourism and travel industry. Although these crises caused serious damage to tourism stakeholders, it was possible for the industry to recover in the medium term (Scott and Laws, 2006; Cheer et al., 2021). However, the COVID-19 crisis, which emerged at the beginning of 2020 and affected the whole world in a short time, has dominated the tourism and travel industry to an unprecedented extent.

During the epidemic period, the supply networks of the tourism sector, businesses and the mobility of their regions have come to a standstill (Atasoy et al., 2022). While the new order that emerged after the pandemic was hopeful for tourism regions and businesses, the Russia-Ukraine war that broke out suddenly knocked the door of tourism with a new crisis. The war suddenly suspended international economic relations.

Shortly after Russia's declaration of war, political, economic and commercial problems arose on a global scale. The claim that Russia will limit its energy exports has increased global crude oil prices, resulting in a price of over \$100 per barrel (Koch, 2022a). The cutting of the Black Sea trade routes has created an increasing pressure on the prices of agricultural products (wheat, corn, barley) (Economist Intelligence Unit, 2022).

In addition, the closure of Russia's airspace caused civilian flights to take an hour or two longer. J. Gradek notes that an extra flight hour incurs an additional cost of between €8,000 and €15,000, which will incur an additional charge of around €100 per seat (Limb, 2022). Lufthansa reported an additional flight time of more than ninety minutes to Seoul and more than two hours to Tokyo, with ticket prices increasing due to increased fuel costs (Mahtani, 2022). These developments appear to be serious problems for the airline industry trying to recover from the pandemic.

The fluctuation in the financial markets indicates that the war will produce various problems for many sectors. One of these sectors is undoubtedly tourism. The war could disappoint global tourism's prospects for recovery and deepen the industry's wounds from the pandemic. The tourism and travel industry will experience not only a loss of employee income but also a shortage of labor and supply. Because the war worries not only Ukraine, but also Europe, the heart of tourism (Tarlow, 2022). The European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) has warned of high

risk as medium or high-range missiles may hit civilian aircraft that may enter the airspace of Ukraine, Russia, Belarus, Poland, Slovakia, Hungary, Romania and Moldova (EASA) (EASA, 2022). This warning can be counted among the first steps of international restrictions that may arise due to war.

Reservation cancellations of both inbound and outbound tourists in Russia and Ukraine were seen as the first and short-term effects of the crisis on the industry. In addition, Norwegian cruise ships (TUI, MSC and AIDA Cruises) suspended all travel to Russia. Phoenix Reisen, a German agency, canceled all cruises along the Volga River for April and May (Koch, 2022b). In response, Russia asked its citizens to stay away from countries that impose sanctions on them and to stop sales to tour operators to these countries (Haro, 2022).

These changing conditions of global tourism have once again demonstrated the importance of being prepared for crises. However, although tourism and crisis research has gained popularity in recent years, there is limited information on how crises affect tourism and how industry responds to it (Cohen and Neal, 2010). Moreover, tourism literature is not at the desired level against major crises such as the pandemic. In the research, it is foreseen to correct this problem and enrich the crisis literature by examining the crises that have had devastating effects on the tourism and travel sector in the past. In this context, the first reactions of global tourism to the Russia-Ukraine crisis were examined and it was explained how the crisis could pose a threat to tourism in the future. In this direction, the research has three interrelated main objectives.

First, the study critically analyzes the literature on the effects of previous terrorism and war-related crises on global tourism. Secondly, the study provides a quick assessment of the effects of the war on global tourism from many aspects until the end of June 2022, especially in the travel, airline, accommodation and food and beverage sectors due to the restrictions imposed by many countries. Finally, the study, which deals with the new effects of the Russia-Ukraine war on global tourism, explores the damage that the war may cause to tourism in the coming years and how the war can change international economies. The crisis is very new, but the effects could be huge. As global markets fluctuate due to the war, the travel and tourism sector is already one of the most damaged international sectors.

2 THEORETICAL REVIEW

2.1 Crises and tourism: Lessons from the past

Global tourism has faced various difficulties arising from different factors during the current period. These difficulties can be listed as the terrorist attacks of September 11 (2001), the global economic crisis (2009), the Japanese Tsunami (2011), the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS, 2015) and the COVID-19 pandemic (Table I).

While some of the crises arise spontaneously in nature, some of them are human induced (Joo et al., 2019; Gössling et al., 2020; Hateftabar and Chapuis, 2020). Although international tourism has suffered from these crises, none

has inflicted as deep a wound as the COVID-19 pandemic. However, the tourism and travel industry, which is trying to heal the wounds of the pandemic, is facing a new crisis.

The tourism industry has faced various crises caused by many factors in the recent periods. Some of these have produced more devastating effects than others. For example, the terrorist attack in the United States of America on September 11, 2001 was a crisis that affected global tourism. The United States limited domestic and foreign tourism by expressing that there was a problem of international trust due to terrorism since tourism is very vulnerable to issues such as security and health. In September, serious cancellations occurred in hotel and airline reservations (Brouder, 2020). This situation was only for the U.S. but also caused a decline in global tourism (Kimani, 2021). That is because the supply and demand factor is an important determinant of tourism mobility. In addition, the issue of the safety of human life comes before tourism. Therefore, the terrorist attacks in the USA hindered the development of global tourism for the relevant period.

The other crisis affecting human health is SARS. SARS, which was first seen in China in 2002, both affected human health and produced an economic crisis. The World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTTC) reported that a total of three million people lost their jobs in the regions of China, Hong Kong, Singapore and Vietnam. The turn of SARS into an epidemic brought along a serious economic crisis by restricting the tourism and travel industry. Even the remaining countries of Asia lost more than 70% of their tourism arrivals (McKercher and Chon, 2004; Rainey et al. 2022).

Also that challenged the tourism and travel industry in the past was the global mortgage crisis between 2008 and 2012. The outbreak of the subprime mortgage crisis closely affected tourism demand (Lu, et al., 2018). The resulting economic crisis caused a significant decline in international tourist arrivals in 2009. Therefore, it is obvious that economic concerns such as health pose a threat to tourism.

Figure 1. Past crises and their reflections on tourism (Milion).

Source: World Bank, 2022.

In the same year, the swine flu (H1N1), which was first detected in Mexico in April 2009, was also another factor damaging the tourism phenomenon. Swine flu, which soon turned into an epidemic, supported the decline in international arrivals (Lee et al., 2012). The H1N1 outbreak hit markets in Northeast Asia and the USA the most. For

example, only Mexico suffered a loss of more than 3 billion Euros and half of this decline was in travel and tourism sectors (Türkay and Atasoy, 2022). Therefore, it should be clearly stated that the economic crisis and swine flu epidemic are behind the 4% decline in global tourism in 2009.

The tsunami disaster (7.3 intensity) is a crisis that negatively affected tourism. While more than 230 thousand people were left homeless, about 20 thousand people lost their lives. One consequence of this disaster was the formation of approximately 20 to 25 million tons of debris, of which only 6% were permanently disposed of one year after the accident. Japan witnessed difficult times for tourism after the earthquake. Departures and arrivals greatly decreased. The issue of people's life and property security explained this situation (Ghaderi and Henderson, 2013).

That was because the biggest fear experienced by tourists visiting Japan was the possibility of coast and beach safety to be affected by natural disasters (Nguyen, 2018). Therefore, effective strategies are required to help tourism businesses and destinations as a whole recover from natural disasters. At this point, it may be vital to design plans and policies that include measures against crises, especially for destination managements and private businesses (Hystad and Keller, 2008; Lin et al., 2018; Fukui and Ohe, 2020; Martini and Minca, 2021).

MERS (Middle East respiratory syndrome) epidemic, which was detected in Saudi Arabia in 2012, made its presence felt worldwide in 2015. This epidemic especially affected the tourism mobility of Far Eastern countries. For example, South Korea is one of the countries affected by the epidemic. The country's tourism hosted 1.53 million less tourists in the months of June-September compared to the previous year. Even these figures reveal how much tourism suffered from the epidemic (Choe et al., 2021; Shi and Li, 2017).

A recent factor affecting the global tourism phenomenon on an unprecedented scale is the COVID-19 pandemic. Expressed as a new type of coronavirus that emerged in Wuhan in 2019, COVID-19 spread to the countries of the world in a very short time. Although epidemics had been seen in the past, none of them had reached the level that was as contagious and threatening to human health as COVID-19. The crisis, with the recognition of COVID-19 as a pandemic by the World Health Organization, has produced an unprecedented pressure on the economy as well as human health. Keeping physical distance, isolating patients and closing international borders to prevent contagion among people have deepened the economic effects (Gössling et al., 2021; Ntounis et al., 2022; Afanasiev ve Afanasieva, 2021; Vidal et al., 2021).

Travel restrictions have directly affected the tourism industry. Seats offered by airlines declined by 50% in 2020. As the number of COVID-19 cases has increased, so have travel bans. Thus, the number of international passengers has also decreased at the same rate. In this process, important airline companies such as Luftansa, Ryanair, Turkish Airlines, Corendon, Delta, Emirates, Qatar airways did not fly (Roman et al., 2022).

Almost all the countries of the world have suffered from the economic effects of the pandemic. In some countries,

international tourism has come to a complete standstill in a large proportion of destinations. Close to 50 million people worldwide lost their jobs in 2020 due to quarantine in various regions. These losses have affected all aspects and actors of the tourism value chain, from destinations to service providers (e.g. airlines, hotels, catering companies and local restaurants) and cultural tourism, ethnic tourism sites (museums) to tourism intermediaries (online travel agencies) (Li et al., 2022).

In Europe, this epidemic crisis has deepened even more since tourism activities in this continent are more intense than other continents. A significant part of the countries that host the most tourists is Europe. After the outbreak of the pandemic, it was observed that European air transport came to a near standstill in the spring of 2020.

Figure 2. Arrivals (in millions) by air passenger transport from EU member states.

Source: Eurostat, 2022a.

While the number of people who stayed overnight in the high season before the epidemic was over 250 million, this number remained below 100 million after the epidemic. This is an indication that EU countries, which are one of the regions with the highest tourist activity, had a difficult time in terms of tourism. In April, May and December, it can be clearly seen that the accommodation industry experienced a great depression. That is because, during this period, when the epidemic reached its peak, many countries imposed travel and curfew restrictions.

Figure 3. Nights spent in tourist accommodation establishments in EU countries (in millions).

Source: Eurostat, 2022b.

2022 is a year when the tourism sector is in crisis. Monkeypox virus epidemic broke out in 2022. The case, which was first seen in London, has moved to other EU countries. The rate of contagion of the disease has increased due to the personal belongings that people use. The disease causes lesions and wounds in infected individuals. To prevent this situation, England does not accept tourists from risk-bearing countries. In addition, the infected person is taken into a 21-day quarantine process (Saied et al., 2022). The World Health Organization declared a global emergency in July 2022. This situation required countries to take measures regarding travel, accommodation and food and beverage at the point of tourism. The possibility of monkeypox to turn into an epidemic while the war continues will also contribute to the decrease in tourism arrivals in 2022.

Figure 4. World Map of Monkeypox Disease.

Source: Saied vd., 2022.

2.2. Russia-Ukraine crisis and its background

Power wars that last for years in the world reveal themselves both economically, militarily and socially (Bartelson, 2021). For example, Russia's view of Ukraine as an influence from the USSR and its desire to maintain its sovereignty caused tensions between the two countries from time to time (Malyarenko and Wolff, 2018). Russia's annexation of Crimea in 2014 further increased this tension and paved the way for a series of developments.

Years later US President J. Biden (February, 2022) announced that he would send 3,000 troops to Poland and Romania to counter the Russian troops stationed on the Ukrainian border and support their NATO allies. In response, Russia has deployed the largest number of troops on the Belarusian border since the cold war period (CFR, 2022).

Due to the increase in tension in the region and the possibility of Russia organizing a military action, many Western political leaders wanted their citizens to return to their countries (BBC, 2022a). On February 21, 2022, Russian President Putin announced to the whole world that Russia officially recognized the two separatist regions in eastern Ukraine, Luhansk and Donetsk, and the country sent peacekeepers to the region (Psaropoulos, 2022). Just three days later, after a television speech by President Putin, a full-scale military operation began and Ukraine's major cities, airports and military headquarters were attacked (Kirby,

2022). Thereupon, the citizens of both countries who were in touristic travels (14,800 people from Russia – 3,000 people from Ukraine Dominican Republic; 20.000 Ukraine-Egypt) had to apply to diplomatic processes to return to their countries (Koch, 2022b). According to the United Nations, as of February 24, 7.3 million Ukrainian citizens immigrated to neighboring countries (UN, 2022).

Immediately after Russia's declaration of war, many western political leaders initiated economic sanctions and initially restricted access to the Russian central bank's \$630 billion reserves. Subsequently, the US, the EU and the UK prevented people and businesses from transacting with the

Russian central bank. Some Russian banks were removed from the Swift system, and a series of sanctions were imposed (BBC, 2022c). While the Central Bank of Russia doubled the interest rate, the Ruble experienced a sharp depreciation. The Kremlin required Russian exporters to exchange 80% of their foreign exchange income with Ruble. Visa and Mastercard have removed sanctioned Russian banks from the payment system (Selyukh, 2022). It can be said that the melting Ruble in the face of these financial strains will weaken the purchasing power of Russian tourists and affect tourism demand.

Table 1. Past crises and their effects on tourism.

Crisis	Place-time/date	Effects of the crisis
September 11 attacks	United States (US) September, 2001	According to IATA (International Airlines Association) after the terrorist attacks, 1/3 of the companies of the airline industry on an international scale have lost flights, passengers and employees. 2973 people lost their lives in 4 separate plane attacks.
SARS	China November, 2002	Air transport and tourism declined significantly, especially in Asia; the recovery began in the third quarter of 2003. 8096 cases of SARS have been reported in 37 countries and 774 deaths have been confirmed.
Economic Crisis	In The World 2009	According to World Tourism Organization data international arrivals decreased by 4% during the 2009 crisis. With the economic crisis, unemployment has been experienced in the tourism sector as in all sectors.
Pandemic (H1N1)	Mexico April, 2009	A new flu virus, which is easily transmitted from person to person, was first detected in Mexico in April 2009. In total, less than 20 000 people died from the virus. Travel and tourism activities have declined sharply due to human-to-human transmission and high media coverage. Mexico's economic loss alone was more than 3 billion euros, half of which was in the travel and tourism sector. International travel and tourism figures only reached pre-2009 pandemic (H1N1) levels in the spring of 2010.
Japan Tsunami	Japan March, 2011	Progress in world tourism has declined by about 5%. While more than 230 thousand people were left homeless, about 20 thousand people lost their lives.
MERS (Middle East respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus)	Saudi Arabia April, 2015	In South Korea, another country where the epidemic was carried, approximately 2.6 billion dollars of tourism income was lost. From June to September 2015, the loss in the number of tourists was about 37%. It has affected many Far East countries, especially South Korea
COVID-19	China December, 2019	The new type of coronavirus that emerged in Wuhan, passing from person to person, spread to many countries in a short time. On March 11, 2020, the outbreak was declared as the COVID-19 pandemic. As of May 30, 2020, 5 796 257 cases were confirmed. As of June 2020, 362 483 people had died in 216 countries from the epidemic, which is still uncontrollable. The COVID-19 outbreak caused a 22% drop in international tourist arrivals in the first three months of 2020. In the year 2020, a decrease of 60% and 80% in tourism is predicted. Tourism is one of the world's major economic sectors. It is the third-largest export category (after fuels and chemicals) and in 2019 accounted for 7% of global trade. A loss of between \$910 million and \$1.2 trillion is expected. It is estimated that there will be around 580 million to 1.1 billion less individuals participating in tourism worldwide. Export revenues from tourism could fall by \$910 billion to \$1.2 trillion in 2020. This will have a wider impact and could reduce global GDP by 1.5% to 2.8%. Worldwide, around 100 million to 120 million people's jobs in tourism and related industries are considered to be at risk. Tourism supports one in 10 jobs and provides a livelihood for millions more in both developing and developed economies. About 120 million people are at risk.
Monkeypox Virus (BBC, 2022b)	London May,2022	There have been reservation cancellations for trips to Europe from all over the world. The United Kingdom has set a quarantine period of 21 days for this disease and has restricted flights from Africa. In the cities where monkeypox is seen in the UK, accommodation establishments provide disposable towels, etc. started to use products. The World Health Organization has declared a global emergency.

Source: own elaboration.

The removal of Russian banks from international payment systems and the continuation of the depreciation of the local currency can be considered to have a restrictive effect on Russia's participation in foreign tourism. A decrease is expected in the number of Russian tourists in many countries, especially in Turkey, Finland, Kazakhstan and China. Travel analysis company ForwardKeys (2022) indicated that reservations made by Russian tourists to various countries, especially Turkey, UAE, Maldives and Thailand, were largely canceled with the start of the war.

The war is damaging global tourism in many ways, not only by the loss of Russian tourists but also by restricting the tourism mobility of Ukrainian citizens. There is a decline in tourism-related reservations in Poland, Hungary and Turkey, which are frequent destinations for Ukrainian tourists (DPSU, 2021).

The country most likely to be affected by the war in terms of tourism is Turkey. Most of Turkey's tourism revenues are derived from both countries. Turkey hosted 4.6 million Russian and 2 million Ukrainian tourists last year. This group, which constitutes the first and third largest tourist group coming to the country, has seen a great decline in Turkish reservations since the outbreak of the war (Hurriyetdaily; 2022). While it was thought that Turkish tourism would revive the tourists coming from both countries after COVID-19, businesses and destinations have already started to search for alternative markets (France24, 2022).

That is because, as a result of the war between these two countries, which make up a quarter of Turkish tourism, there will be a sharp decrease of 30% according to the sector representatives (Dailysabah; 2022). However, on the other hand, the fact that Turkey does not impose any restrictions against Russian tourists may create a great demand for tourism in the country. For now, there is no abnormal change in the number of arrivals of Russian tourists. However, the crisis is very fresh, and it is not possible to say its effects quantitatively at the moment.

European countries are quite ahead in terms of tourist arrivals compared to other countries. However, the outbreak of war and the possibility of spreading to Europe may weaken tourism in the region. Among the main reasons for this decrease include the increase in oil and transportation costs due to the war, life safety and bureaucratic obstacles. The fact that tourism countries such as Turkey, Germany, France, Italy and Spain are close to Russia and Ukraine worries future tourists.

The fact that the war takes place at points close to these countries highlights the security issue of these destinations. On the other hand, it is clear that Russia and Ukraine, as one of the important actors of global tourism, both receiving and sending tourists, will cause serious wounds for the tourism industry. That is because even if the war ends, it will take a long time for the perception of security to be placed in the public opinion. During this period, accommodation, travel and catering businesses have to survive with domestic tourism.

The growing wave of migration due to the crisis has revealed an important refugee problem after Syria. European countries provide serious economic assistance to solve the refugee problem, but the desire to protect cultural differences and demographic balances indicates that the crisis will

produce various effects on societies. In summary, although the crisis is very fresh, it can be said that it has severe effects on political and economic balances, especially on tourism.

3 METHODOLOGY

This research was carried out in order to critically examine the literature on the effects of past crises on the tourism sector and to quickly reveal the damage caused by the Russia-Ukraine crisis to the tourism and travel sector. Although a relatively recent event, data from secondary sources have been obtained to show the rapidly emerging effects of the crisis. Systematic review technique was used in the data collection process. A systematic review requires a comprehensive classification of many studies or documents carried out by experts in the relevant field (Karaçam, 2013). This type of research is conducted to systematically research, compare and analyze studies related to a specific event or phenomenon and to provide a conceptual framework (Ercan, 2020).

In order to reach the scientific data needed by the research, first of all, databases were examined. Then, the keywords and resource types were determined and the databases were searched. During the research process, it was realized that the crisis had just emerged and that sufficient scientific articles had not been published yet. Thereupon, reports, newspapers and statistical studies were included in the data process of the research. Data includes studies performed or prepared up to 24 June 2022. The current review is guided by the following research questions (RQs):

- *RQ1: What are the initial effects of the Russia-Ukraine crisis on the tourism and travel industry?*
- *RQ2: Which countries' tourism and travel sectors have been severely damaged by the Russia-Ukraine crisis? Is there a decline in world tourism?*
- *RQ3: How will the Russia-Ukraine crisis shape the tourism and travel industry in the future? What lessons should the tourism sector and public administrators learn from this crisis?*

4 FINDINGS

4.1 Possible Effects of the Russian-Ukrainian Crisis on Tourism

According to the United Nations report, as of January 2022, the total loss of people in the war is between 13,100 and 13,300 people. This number is taken as 3,375 civilian deaths, approximately 4,150 Ukrainian military deaths and approximately 5,700 pro-Russian fighters. About 2 million people have been internally displaced in Ukraine, and more than 7% of Ukrainian territory has been occupied (UN, 2022). How the war will develop during the year and the issue of peace remain uncertain, these forecasts need to be comprehensively addressed. In particular, the wounds of the crisis, while intensifying in Europe, may cause great job losses globally.

According to UNWTO (2022a), the crisis is expected to result in a loss of approximately 14 billion USD in the tourism

economy. The main concern here is that the crisis caused by the Russian-Ukrainian war does not allow the industry to heal its wounds. Although countries have implemented significant financial programs on a national basis, it remains unclear how this will benefit the tourism sector. In the sections below, expectations and implications for various branches of the tourism and travel industry are given. It was aimed to clarify the issue by discussing the possible scenarios of the crisis in different branches such as travel, accommodation, food-and-beverage and entertainment.

4.1.1 Travel

The most important determinant of the tourism phenomenon is travel. Because people's visit to different places depends on their change of place. Today, global tourism is on a scale that transcends international borders. Therefore, the war-related crisis and the restrictions imposed prevented people from traveling, causing the first blow to tourism. During the COVID-19 pandemic, airline companies survived by receiving state aid. For example, the German tour operator TUI received over US\$15 billion in state aid. In addition, the USA provided 50 billion dollars support to airline companies for civil flights (Gössling et al., 2020).

With the start of the war, more than 30 countries, including the EU, Canada and France, closed their airspace to Russian airlines such as Aeroflot, Azur Air and Ural.

Figure 5. Countries that have closed their airspace to Russia.

Source: Bussinessinsider, 2022.

Then, Russia took a decision against it and announced that it closed its airspace for 36 countries including Germany, England, France, Belgium, Spain, Netherlands, Italy and Canada. It is inevitable that these developments will reduce international tourist arrivals. The stated countries wanted to make the dimensions of the possible war more minimal by closing their airspaces. Thus, it was aimed to prevent the possibility of the crisis turning into a 3rd World War. However, these actions produce overwhelming effects in terms of tourism. Travel barriers will reduce the flow of tourists to the region.

On the other hand, the fact that the two countries are close to Europe increases the security concerns of tourists coming to the region (Pandey and Kumar, 2022). Therefore, these actions will affect the global tourism activity negatively

in a short time and will deepen the wounds of the crisis. The loss of Russian and Ukrainian tourists, who spent a total of US\$45 billion a year (about eight percent of the global total) before the Covid-19 pandemic, will affect many countries in developing Europe. This is because Baltic and European Countries are imposing sanctions on Russian tourists. Therefore, it becomes difficult to travel (Emerging Europe, 2023).

The war, which started with the military operation of Russia, turned into a global crisis in a short time. Mutual political moves between many western countries and Russia caused travel rates to drop in a short time. In addition, the possibility of the war spreading to European countries and the fact that some countries neighboring Ukraine were not perceived as a safe destination caused a sharp decline in airline transportation figures. Countries that have experienced the greatest decline in flight numbers since the beginning of the crisis can be listed as Moldova (69%), Slovenia (42%), Lithuania (38%) (Figure 6). Considering other countries, a decline in EU tourism can be mentioned.

Figure 6. European countries with largest decline in number of flights

Source: UNWTO, 2022b.

4.1.2 Accommodation

The war between Russia and Ukraine soon turned into an international crisis. Concern for the safety of people's life and property, airspaces closed to civil flights, and increased transportation costs due to oil have directly damaged the tourism and travel industry. It is thought that the accommodation industry, which is the main branch of tourism, will also be affected by the less participation of Ukrainian and Russian tourists in global tourism.

The contraction on the demand side will make its impact felt especially in international travels. There are already serious contractions in travel to neighboring countries. On the other hand, the accommodation industry also faces some challenges in terms of supply. For example, chain hotel companies also supported the sanctions against Russia.

Some global hospitality businesses such as Hyatt, Marriott, Hilton and InterContinental Hotels Group (IHG) have suspended their investments in Russia. However, Marriott, IHG and Hilton closed their Moscow offices and announced

that they would support their employees in order not to be victimized (Turner, 2022).

Therefore, the Russian Federation, where visitors from abroad are limited, has been deprived of the support of global companies in terms of accommodation for the time being. On the Ukrainian side, people and businesses are leaving the countries. In the country where the war is getting more intense every day, the migration wave is one of the difficulties faced by the neighboring countries. While low tourism figures are emerging for both countries, a serious decrease is expected in the number of tourists going abroad. It is a rather uncertain picture at the moment to say how international travel will take shape and to what extent there will be a regression.

It is inevitable to see that the impact on the accommodation market is worse for the highly connected ones, given the fact that the accommodation markets are falling further but the economies are dependent on the tourism demand of Russia and Ukraine. Ukraine's bombing of Moscow and Russia's retaliatory bombing of certain points in Kiev worries tourists (Balli et al, 2023).

4.1.3 Sports Events

The war that broke out between Russia and Ukraine affected many industries in a short time. Organization and realization of global events in tourism is an important issue. The war has damaged the tourism phenomenon in terms of these activities. For example, Russia and Ukraine have been deprived of income from sporting events (Wong and Chadwick, 2017). FIFA banned the teams of the two countries from European cups and imposed a serious economic sanction in terms of both tourism and sports. Because in sports organizations, millions of people visit different countries and contribute to the development of global tourism and destinations. From this point of view, this decision of FIFA reveals a serious loss for both countries economically. Russia was disqualified from important competitions such as Formula-1 Grand-pix and Eurovision music competition. It has also been decided that the 2021-2022 Champions League final match will be held in Paris, the capital of France, instead of Saint Petersburg, Russia. In this respect, it can be said that especially Russia will experience serious losses in tourist arrivals and tourism revenues will decrease.

4.1.4 Food and Beverage Businesses

In Ukraine, which is facing the devastating effects of the war, food and beverage services are at a standstill. Aid is provided by the state to the local people who provide life safety in the shelters. Some famous restaurants provide free meals to protect their citizens. For example, Milk Bar distributes free meals to the citizens of the Capital throughout the day (Timmins, 2022). LaFamiglia Group, consisting of 14 restaurants, tries to meet the nutritional needs of the people by distributing 8,000 snacks and 5000 sandwiches every day.

These businesses, which earn billions of dollars, are striving to stand by their country beyond facing serious financial losses since the war. On the other hand, while the

Russian Federation and food-beverage companies are actively working, some global companies make harsh moves. McDonald's, one of the largest burger chains in the world, has announced that it will sell all its restaurants in Russia. The big giant, which was among the fast-food businesses that came to the fore during the pandemic period, stated that it took an attitude against the war by withdrawing from Russia (Phillips, 2022).

In the past 32 years, McDonald's has employed 62,000 people and opened 847 restaurants. Similarly, another global chain company, Starbucks, which has spread to 130 different locations in the country, has decided to withdraw from the Russian market. The company, which employs 2,000 personnel, stopped working by citing the war (Barry, 2022). These figures may cause some problems for the Russian Federation to the point of employment and catering.

The inability to use the agricultural lands of the occupied Ukrainian lands and the inability to export products such as barley and wheat have created serious problems for some countries. Russia's export of oil, grain, etc. to other countries and restricting its sales and controlling the logistics mobility of the Black Sea have revealed the global food and supply crisis.

This situation created inflationary pressure on the prices of some basic nutrition products such as oil, barley, wheat, corn and bread in the countries importing from both countries. Therefore, many countries had to bear economic costs of the war. Actions such as the increase in oil prices and the closure of the airspace of many countries increased the transportation costs, and indirectly, the prices of agricultural products showed a tendency to increase. Although Turkey has stepped in to solve the global food crisis, many countries are already facing serious problems regarding grain.

4.1.5 Cruises

Crises based on war, terrorism and health affect various branches of the tourism industry. One of these areas is cruise tourism, which has been seriously affected by the war between Russia and Ukraine. Due to the deepening of the war, many global companies canceled their trips to various ports, especially Russia and Ukraine. By mistake, some companies have moved citizens who immigrated from Ukraine to some European countries. In terms of global tourism, while tourism arrivals decreased in regions where voyages were canceled, cruisers turned their routes to other destinations. Thus, some idle ports started to host more tourists. In both cases, there is a decline in tourism mobility.

Celebrity Cruises cancelled its St. Petersburg trips; the company changed the route to Sweden. Carnival Corporation and MSC Cruise have suspended flights to Russia. Regent Seven Seas Cruises, stopped all its travels to the ports of St. Petersburg and Odessa. As one of the global companies, Viking River Cruises canceled all its tours from Kyiv and Bucharest this year. Atlas Ocean Voyages has stated that this year the company will organize voyages to Finland and Estonia instead of Russian ports (Coulter, 2022).

The apparent scenario is that the crisis will lead to a contraction in supply and demand in cruise tourism. Orientation of companies to destinations that are considered

safe will support purchases. However, the creation of tour programs and new package deals will take time and effort. Some countries can turn the crisis into an opportunity to host more tourists. For example, the cruise companies can contribute to the development of new routes by submitting offers for the development of package tours and services.

With the Ukraine-Russia war, the security of the ports has become problematic. They met in Istanbul on July 22, 2022. At the meeting, which brought Ukraine and Russia together for the first time after the invasion, the "Secure Shipment of Grain and Foodstuffs from Ukrainian Ports Initiative Document" was signed (Yenginar, 2022). While there is a problem with food, which is a compulsory need, cruise ships coming for tourism travels experience bigger problems. In addition, European countries still do not accept cruises from Russia.

4.2 Implications for Post-Crisis Global Tourism

Immediately after the outbreak of the Russia-Ukraine war, seven million Ukrainian migrants crossed into border countries, global markets fluctuated, logistics of some products were suspended, and the tourism and travel industry witnessed various difficulties.

The National Institute of Economic and Social Research (2022:1) expresses the economic effects of the crisis for countries as follows: the war will reduce global GDP by one percent and cost about US\$1 trillion in losses. The supply of products such as titanium, palladium, wheat and corn by both states will cause supply problems for many industries (car, smartphone, aircraft manufacturers and so on).

While dependence on Russian energy and food worries European countries, the crisis is more damaging for developing countries. Europe's support for immigrants and military spending on Ukraine will produce pressure on GDP. On the other hand, the economic sanctions bill for Russia could turn into a contraction of more than 2.5% by the end of 2023. As the war continues, inflationary pressure has already revealed the impact of the crisis for every economy.

Moreover, the international community is facing an economic crisis once again as it heals the economic wounds left behind by the COVID-19 pandemic. In summary, the effects of the war on global industries are in the form of decrease in demand due to the increase in food and energy prices, the interruption of international trade and the pressure on asset prices due to investor anxiety.

Undoubtedly, tourism is one of the industries most affected by the crises (Santana, 2004). The reason is that tourism includes people's economy and related travel (Hall, 2010). However, mutual sanctions between Western countries and Russia have dealt the first blow to the travel and tourism industry by limiting air, ship and land transportation. For example, the fact that more than 30 countries closed their airspace to Russia prevented both Russian tourists from leaving the country and foreign travelers from entering the country.

The claim that Russia will limit the energy supply has increased oil and gas prices. While this situation contributed to the fact that flights were more expensive and included additional time, it also increased the material and moral costs

of people.

The decrease in reservations of countries working in the Russian and Ukrainian markets hindered the need for recovery after the pandemic. While many countries have turned to alternative markets, the possibility of the war approaching the center of Europe has pushed global tourism into uncertainty. While the cruisers turn their routes to the west of the Mediterranean, the Black Sea and the east of the Mediterranean are waiting for a difficult season in terms of tourism.

For this reason, the Russia-Ukraine war urges countries to consider the success of tourism which is associated with growth. WTO mentions two scenarios in which global tourism figures will decrease between 50% and 63% in 2022 depending on the course of the war. This indicates how serious the damage the war will cause to the tourism industry. While tourism arrival rates remain uncertain, the decline in airline travel and holiday reservations supports the relevant forecast.

After the crisis, everyone will have learned a lesson already. The resilience of tourism destinations, which depend on a single market in the first place, will come to the fore. However, instead of being dependent on a single market, dealing with many markets requires product diversity (Ziyadin et al., 2019). Benur & Bramwell (2015) indicate that the diversification and mutual integration of the primary factors that attract tourists to tourism regions increase the competitiveness of destinations and support their sustainability.

In a scenario where Europe, as the heart of tourism, is uncertain in global tourism, Asian markets are likely to come to the fore. An approach that takes into account the characteristics and expectations of developing or underdeveloped countries and the Asian market will be beneficial. At the same time, holiday programs appealing to different countries of Europe will increase the power of destinations. It is significant for countries that are economically dependent on tourism to produce various conditions for domestic tourism in the face of the decline in tourists from both states. That is because, compared to the international travel and tourism industry, domestic tourism dynamics can react in a short time.

Figure 7. International tourist arrivals: 2020, 2021 and scenarios for 2022.

Source: UNWTO, 2022b.

Tour operators, accommodation businesses, travel agencies, restaurants and other tourism businesses have witnessed the effects of war depending on the destination. While the tourism of some countries is more deeply injured by the war, some countries can turn the crisis into an opportunity. This situation raises the issue of the reliability of tourism regions. The issue of travel safety is a requirement for understanding tourist behavior in the wake of the crisis.

Accordingly, the element that shapes tourist perceptions is the reliability of vacation and transportation to the destination to be visited. Tourists tend to cancel their travels and avoid the affected tourism areas and return home from the region where the crisis occurred in the event of a security risk arising from the crisis (Mansfeld & Pizam, 2006).

Especially in some countries of the Mediterranean, the serious problems that tourism has faced in the past years are security problems caused by terrorism (Drakos & Kutan, 2003). Wachyuni & Kusumaningrum's view that tourism will continue as a necessity after the COVID-19 pandemic is valid for the Russia-Ukraine war. However, security is an issue that is at the center of the world, not just tourism.

Global security concerns produce a broader economic and political impact beyond individual tourism decisions (Hall et al., 2004). Therefore, the argument by Khalid et al., (2021) that public aids are needed to sustain businesses suffering deep damage from tourism during the pandemic is also valid for healing the wounds of the war-born crisis. As long as the war does not end, the economic and social costs of the crisis will multiply. Therefore, global tourism demand may experience a significant loss of demand.

5 CONCLUSION

This research basically presents a quick assessment of the impact of the Russia-Ukraine crisis on global tourism and critically discusses the literature examining the relationship between past crises and tourism. Crisis studies in tourism often talk about long-term effects. However, the first responses of tourism to the crisis are important for the development and monitoring of medium and long-term strategies. Therefore, it is thought that the crisis and tourism literature will expand with the conceptual approach presented in this study.

RQ1: What are the initial effects of the Russia-Ukraine crisis on the tourism and travel industry?

The war, which started with the entry of Russian military units into the territory of Ukraine, turned into a global crisis. In just a few days, international politics and economies showed how big the problem was with their extraordinary response to the crisis caused by the war. When it comes to the travel and tourism industry, it is worth noting that the industry is facing another devastation following the COVID-19 pandemic.

Tourism is a sector that reacts immediately to crises such as terrorism and war, but takes many years to recover (Sönmez et al., 1999; Henderson, 2007; Martens et al., 2016). The Russia-Ukraine war limited the international tourism mobility in a short time and many destinations and tourism businesses suddenly suffered serious losses. While the travel industry loses hope of recovery after the pandemic, the cessation of purchases for both countries reveals the wounds of tourism. Closed airspaces have restricted people's

international travel, or people have had to endure more flight time and cost due to the need to develop different flight routes. While these developments only cast a shadow on people's participation in tourism, foreign travels of Russian and Ukrainian tourists were also canceled and came to a halt. Local tour operators delayed travel and vacation planning, while western tour operators canceled almost all Russia-Ukraine flights. As cruisers change routes, tourism occupancy rates for some countries drop drastically.

RQ2: Which countries' tourism and travel sectors have been severely damaged by Russia-Ukraine crisis? Is there a decline in the world tourism?

In terms of tourism, the countries that suffered the most from the crisis were the parties to the war. Tourism seems far away for the citizens of Ukraine, who have had to leave their millions of homes and countries. On the other hand, the restriction of the Russian Federation's travel options, which are restricted by many western countries, and rising costs seem to have affected tourism arrivals. Therefore, considering the conditions in both countries, a regression in international arrivals seems inevitable.

While the pandemic that has shaken the world for more than two years has not completely disappeared, the crisis that broke out experienced a great decrease in the number of tourists coming to the Russian Federation as of February. Travel restrictions from the US and Europe have shrunk Russia's tourism market and lost its former popularity for western tourists.

The main reason for this is that it is not possible for Russia to use closed air spaces and various banking systems (Mastercard, Visa). For example, with the onset of the crisis, there was a major meltdown in cruise tours to countries such as Latvia and Estonia, and one reason for this was St. Petersburg from the tour itinerary. As Russia's important tourism market, the number of Chinese, German and Turkish tourists can be expected to decrease significantly in 2022.

Because people's security concerns can hinder their desire to travel. It is difficult to give precise information for now, but current conditions show that Russia will encourage domestic tourism rather than foreign tourism market. While some countries experience contraction in demand and loss of supply due to the crisis, this is also the case when this situation turns into an advantage.

For example, the fact that various countries such as Turkey, Egypt, Tunisia and the UAE do not impose any restrictions on the Russian Federation will stimulate the demand for these countries. Especially Turkey and Greece are very dependent on Russian tourists. Therefore, they will need to revise their marketing strategies to attract the attention of Russian tourists.

RQ3: How will the Russia-Ukraine crisis shape the tourism and travel industry in the future? What lessons should the tourism sector and public administrators learn from this crisis?

It may be premature to say that the crisis will harm many industries, especially travel and tourism, for many years, but the deepening of the crisis will contribute to this outcome. The unprecedented economic sanctions will unleash a severe contraction for all industries. Gössling et al., (2020) reported that, after the COVID-19 pandemic, it was obvious that issues such as international borders, economic

recovery, durable tourism destinations, tourist behavior and financial incentives would come to the fore more strongly after the war. Because the Russia-Ukraine war poses a serious threat to the development of the United Nations' sustainable development goals such as hunger, poverty, education, gender equality, labor supply and demand, economic growth, and the construction of sustainable cities and societies.

Although the war is now in the east of Europe, it should not be forgotten that even a society with no interest will have its share of financial fluctuations, which will have to heal its wounds after the crisis. Hall's (2010) mention that any crisis changes global politics and economy due to the mutual integration of elements such as international transportation systems, communication networks, and import-export can clarify this argument.

The inherent fragility of the industry reduces the expectations of developing countries from tourism. Uncertainty is high about the vital sustainability of tourism destinations and companies working in the Russian and Ukrainian markets. It may be difficult for Turkish tourism, which meets the most tourism demand from these two countries, to experience the post-pandemic revival. On the other hand, the fact that many Western countries closed their borders to Russia has contributed to the increasing interest of Russian tour operators in Turkey. Therefore, tourism of diversified countries is more resilient and sustainable against the crisis, rather than being dependent on one market.

After the crisis, the issue of market diversity will come to the fore in the tourism policies of countries. Countries such as China, India, Indonesia, Japan and Hong Kong can turn into attractive markets for international tourism as an alternative to Europe. Just as in previous terrorism, wars and crises, the Russia-Ukraine war has seriously damaged tourism, on the other hand, tourism managers have taught important lessons to their regions and businesses.

The main problem that appears is that the deepening of the crisis will restrict the social development of countries, reveal cultural conflicts caused by migration waves, and the possibility of Europe withdrawing from global tourism, which creates tourism demand in case the war spreads to other countries. After the war, nothing will be the same as before. Therefore, it is a true argument by Sönmez et al. (1999) that crisis management cannot prevent war, terrorism or crisis, but crisis action plans must be prepared in order to reduce the damage that societies will take from any crisis. The reason is that many crises show various symptoms before they occur, and it is vital that all stakeholders perceive these signals, regardless of countries, tourism destinations or strategists (Paraskavas and Altınay, 2013).

The European Union and the World Tourism Organization can open tourism offices to reduce the impact of this crisis. By providing large funds, it can support both the tourism supply and tourism demand of war-affected countries. Financial support can be provided to tourism practitioners of developing countries, which are especially dependent on the Russian and Ukrainian tourism market. Collaboration with tour operators can be conducted to redesign package tours due to tourism destinations removed from tour routes. This could contribute to minimizing the damage done by war to global tourism.

5.1 Limitations and guidelines for future studies

The biggest limitation of the research is that it includes an early assessment of the Russia-Ukraine war. The global effects of the crisis arising from the war will be more pronounced in the long run. While this study presents the current, short-term effects of the crisis, long-term implications are hypothetical. Therefore, it is clear that more research will be needed.

Future studies can reveal the real losses by making statistical measurements of the effects of the war on global tourism. In the travel industry, it is a matter of curiosity how tour operators and travel agencies, as well as air, land and sea transport, were affected by the crisis. However, there is a need to draw a clear picture of the position of global tourism, including tourism destinations and small and large enterprises, after the crisis. However, the crisis in the east of Europe has brought about social transformations as well as the economy.

The socio-psychological or sociological effects of the crisis should also be considered. The social problems of the crisis, such as hunger, impoverishment, loss of life and property, and the problem of immigrants, deepened by the war, can be explored in depth in light of qualitative techniques.

REFERENCES

- Afanasiev, O.E. and Afanasieva, A.V. (2021). Tourism industry in Russia and global covid-19 pandemic: threats, counteractions, trends, *Anais Brasileiros de Estudos Turisticos-ABET*, 11, 1-16.
- Atasoy, B., Türkay, O. and Şengül, S. (2022). Strategic responses of chain hotels to COVID-19 from a situational crisis communication theory perspective. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 5(5), 1118-1136.
- Balli, F., Billah, M. and Chowdhury, I. (2022). Impact of the Russia-Ukraine war on hospitality equity markets. *Tourism Economics*, 0(0), 1-10.
- Barry, E. (2022). *As Starbucks Exits Russia, Another Symbol of American Capitalism Fades*, available at: <https://time.com/6180652/starbucks-mcdonalds-russia-ukraine/> (accessed 27 July 2022).
- Bartelson, J. (2021), War in international relations and return to history I. *Routledge Handbook of Historical International Relations* Routledge, London, 127-137.
- BBC, (2022a), "Ukraine tensions: A dozen nations tell citizens to leave Ukraine", available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-60361983> (accessed 07 March 2022).
- BBC, (2022b), "Monkeypox virus", available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/health-62279436> (accessed 27 July 2022).
- BBC, (2022c), "Ukraine: What sanctions are being imposed on Russia?", available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-60125659> (accessed 08 March 2022).
- Benur, A. M. and Bramwell, B. (2015), "Tourism product development and product diversification in destinations". *Tourism Management*, Vol. 50, pp. 213-224.
- Blane B. (2022), "[How the travel industry is responding to Russia's invasion of Ukraine | CNN Travel](https://edition.cnn.com/travel/article/travel-world-response-ukraine-invasion/index.html)", available at: <https://edition.cnn.com/travel/article/travel-world-response-ukraine-invasion/index.html> (accessed 02 March 2022).

- Brouder, P. (2020), "Reset redux: Possible evolutionary pathways towards the transformation of tourism in a COVID-19 world". *Tourism Geographies*, Vol. 22, No.3, pp. 484-490.
- Bussinessinsider, (2022), "Countries that have closed their airspace to Russia", available at: <https://www.businessinsider.com/map-shows-countries-that-closed-airspace-russia-over-ukraine-war-2022-3> (accessed 28 July 2022).
- Carlsen, J. C. and Liburd, J. J. (2008). Developing a research agenda for tourism crisis management, market recovery and communications. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 23(2-4), 265-276.
- CFR, (2022), "Conflict in Ukraine. global conflict tracker", available at: <https://www.cfr.org/global-conflict-tracker/conflict/conflict-ukraine> (accessed 09 March 2022).
- Cheer, J. M., Lapointe, D., Mostafanezhad, M. and Jamal, T. (2021). Global tourism in crisis: conceptual frameworks for research and practice. *Journal of Tourism Futures*, 7(3), 278-294.
- Choe, Y., Wang, J. and Song, H. (2021), The impact of the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus on inbound tourism in South Korea toward sustainable tourism, *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 29(7), 1117-1133.
- Cohen, E. and Neal, M. (2010). Coinciding crises and tourism in contemporary Thailand. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 13(5), 455-475.
- Coulter, A. (2022), "Cruise lines alter Russia itineraries, provide aid due to Ukraine conflict", available at: <https://www.cruisecritic.com/news/6788/> (accessed 28 July 2022).
- Dailysabah, (2022), "Turkey's tourism sector to pay price for Russia-Ukraine war". available at: <https://www.dailysabah.com/business/tourism/turkeys-tourism-sector-to-pay-price-for-russia-ukraine-war> (accessed 15 March 2022).
- DPSU, (2021), "2020: Where Ukrainians travelled most often, where foreigners came from". available at: <https://dpsu.gov.ua/en/news/2020-where-ukrainians-travelled-most-often-where-foreigners-came-from/> (accessed 14 March 2022).
- Drakos, K. and Kutan, A. M. (2003), Regional effects of terrorism on tourism in three Mediterranean countries. *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 47(5), 621-641.
- EASA, (2022), "Conflict Zone Information Bulletin". available at: <https://www.easa.europa.eu/domains/air-operations/czibs/czib-2022-01> (accessed 06 March 2022).
- Economist Intelligence Unit, (2022), "Global economic implications of the Russia-Ukraine war". available at: <https://www.eiu.com/n/global-economic-implications-of-the-russia-ukraine-war/> (accessed 10 March 2022).
- Emerging, E. (2023). How Russia's war on Ukraine impacts travel and tourism available at: <https://emerging-europe.com/news/how-russias-war-on-ukraine-impacts-travel-and-tourism/> (accessed 8 August 2023).
- Ercan, F. (2020). Akıllı turizmde büyük veri kullanımı: Sistematiik bir derleme. *OPUS International Journal of Society Researches*, 16(32), 5230-5249.
- Eurostat, (2022a), "Air transport statistics" available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Air_transport_statistics (accessed 28 July 2022).
- Eurostat, (2022b), "Tourism statistics - nights spent at tourist accommodation establishments" available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statisticsexplained/index.php?title=Tourism_statistics_nights_spent_at_tourist_accommodation_establishments (accessed 28 July 2022).
- ForwardKeys, (2022), "Russian travellers on the move in Asia". available at: <https://forwardkeys.com/russian-travellers-on-the-move-in-asia/> (accessed 11 March 2022)
- France24, (2022). "Turkey tourism recovery hurt by Russia invasion of Ukraine" available at: <https://www.france24.com/en/live-news/20220306-turkey-tourism-recovery-hurt-by-russia-invasion-of-ukraine> (accessed 07 March 2022).
- Fukui, M. and Ohe, Y. (2020), Assessing the role of social media in tourism recovery in tsunami-hit coastal areas in Tohoku, Japan. *Tourism Economics*, 26(5), 776-791.
- Ghaderi, Z. and Henderson, J. C. (2013), Japanese tsunami debris and the threat to sustainable tourism in the Hawaiian Islands. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 8, 98-105.
- Gössling, S., Scott, D. and Hall, C. M. (2020), Pandemics, tourism and global change: a rapid assessment of COVID-19. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 29(1), 1-20.
- Hall, C. M. (2010), Crisis events in tourism: Subjects of crisis in tourism. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 13(5), 401-417.
- Hall, C. M., Timothy, D. J. and Duval, D. T. (2004), Security and tourism: towards a new understanding?. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 5(2-3), 1-18.
- Haro, Rocío. (2022), Russia-Ukraine conflict: How will the developing conflict affect tourism?, available at: <https://alandistravel.com/trends/russia-ukraine-conflict-effect-on-tourism> (accessed 14 May 2022).
- Hateftabar, F. and Chapuis, J. M. (2020), How resident perception of economic crisis influences their perception of tourism. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 43, 157-168.
- Henderson, J. C. (2007), "Tourism crises: Causes, Consequences and Management". London, Routledge.
- Hurriyetdaily, (2022), "Local tourism industry closely watching Ukraine war". available at: <https://www.hurriyetdailynews.com/local-tourism-industry-closely-watching-ukraine-war-171953> (accessed 15 March 2022).
- Hystad, P. W. and Keller, P. C. (2008), Towards a destination tourism disaster management framework: Long-term lessons from a forest fire disaster. *Tourism Management*, 29(1), 151-162.
- Joo, H., Maskery, B. A., Berro, A. D., Rotz, L. D., Lee, Y. K. and Brown, C. M. (2019), Economic impact of the 2015 MERS outbreak on the Republic of Korea's tourism-related industries. *Health Security*, 17 (2), 100-108.
- Karaçam, Z. (2013). Sistematiik derleme metodolojisi: Sistematiik derleme hazırlamak için bir rehber. *Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi Hemşirelik Fakültesi Elektronik Dergisi*, 6 (1), 26-33.
- Khalid, U., Okafor, L. E. and Burzynska, K. (2021), Does the size of the tourism sector influence the economic policy response to the COVID-19 pandemic?. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 24(19), 2801-2820.
- Kimani, J. (2021), Effect of civil war on the performance of tourism industry in Africa. A Critical literature review. *International Journal of Modern Hospitality and Tourism*, 1(1), 1-15.
- Koch, M. (2022a), "Ukraine: What Russia's war means for the global travel industry". available at: <https://www.dw.com/en/ukraine-what-russias-war-means-for-the-global-travel-industry/a-60987329> (accessed 10 March 2022).
- Koch, M. (2022b), "Russian, Ukrainian tourists stranded abroad amid war back home". available at: <https://www.dw.com/en/russian-ukrainian-tourists-stranded-abroad-amid-war-back-home/a-61021285> (accessed 11 March 2022).
- Lee, C. K., Song, H. J., Bendle, L. J., Kim, M. J. and Han, H. (2012), The impact of non-pharmaceutical interventions for 2009 H1N1 influenza on travel intentions: A model of goal-directed behavior. *Tourism Management*, 33(1), 89-99.

- Li, S., Wang, Y., Filieri, R. ve Zhu, Y. (2022), "Eliciting positive emotion through strategic responses to COVID-19 crisis: Evidence from the tourism sector". *Tourism Management*, 90,1-14.
- Limb, L. (2022), "How will Russia's invasion of Ukraine affect flight paths, journey times and ticket prices?". available at: <https://www.euronews.com/travel/2022/03/01/how-will-russia-s-invasion-of-ukraine-affect-flight-paths-journey-times-and-ticket-prices> (accessed 05 March 2022).
- Lin, Y., Kelemen, M. and Tresidder, R. (2018), Post-disaster tourism: building resilience through community-led approaches in the aftermath of the 2011 disasters in Japan. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 26(10), 1766-1783.
- Lu, C. L., Chen, S. T. and Kuo, H. I. (2018), International tourism demand in Asia: Before and after the economic crisis. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 23(11), 1073-1085.
- Mahtani, M. (2022), "How Russia's invasion of Ukraine could hurt travel's recovery". available at: <https://edition.cnn.com/travel/article/russia-ukraine-hurt-travel-recovery-cmd/index.html> (accessed 06 March 2022).
- Malyarenko, T. and Wolff, S. (2018), The logic of competitive influence-seeking: Russia, Ukraine, and the conflict in Donbas. *Post-Soviet Affairs*, 34(4), 191-212.
- Mansfeld, Y. and Pizam, A. (2006), *Tourism, Security and Safety*. London, Routledge.
- Martens, H. M., Feldesz, K., and Merten, P. (2016), Crisis management in tourism—a literature based approach on the proactive prediction of a crisis and the implementation of prevention measures. *Athens Journal of Tourism*, 3(2), 89-101.
- Martini, A. and Minca, C. (2021), Affective dark tourism encounters: Rikuzentakata after the 2011 great East Japan disaster. *Social & Cultural Geography*, 22(1), 33-57.
- McKercher, B. and Chon, K. (2004), The over-reaction to SARS and the collapse of Asian tourism. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 31(3), 716-719.
- Mutlu, Ç. and Akbaş, Z. (2016), The effect of international terrorism on tourism through the September 11 attacks: The case of Turkey. *Duzce University Journal of Social Sciences Institute*, 6(2),1- 14.
- Navarrete, D., De La Torre, M. I. and Velasco Ávalos, M. (2020). Crime against visitors, its causes and effects in tourist-heritage centres: the case of Guanajuato, Mexico. *Latin American Journal of Tourismology*, 6(1), 1-14.
- Nguyen, D. N., Imamura, F. and Iuchi, K. (2018), Barriers towards hotel disaster preparedness: Case studies of post 2011 Tsunami, Japan. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 28, 585-594.
- Ntounis, N., Parker, C., Skinner, H., Steadman, C. and Warnaby, G. (2022), Tourism and Hospitality industry resilience during the Covid-19 pandemic: Evidence from England. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 25(1), 46-59.
- Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe, (2022), "Russia-Ukraine war" <https://www.osce.org/> (accessed 28 July 2022).
- Pandey, D. K. and Kumar, R. (2022), Russia-Ukraine War and the global tourism sector: A 13-day tale. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 26(5), 1-9.
- Paraskevas, A. and Altınay, L. (2013), Signal detection as the first line of defence in tourism crisis management. *Tourism Management*, 34, 158-171.
- Phillips, A. (2022), "Ukraine war: McDonald's to exit Russia and sell all of its restaurants", available at: <https://news.sky.com/story/ukraine-war-mcdonalds-to-exit-russia-and-sell-all-of-its-restaurants-12614554>. (accessed 28 July 2022).
- Psaropoulos, J. (2022), "Timeline: Week one of Russia's invasion of Ukraine", available at: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2022/3/2/timeline-week-one-of-russia-invasion-of-ukraine> (accessed 07 March 2022).
- Rainey, A. L., Loeb, J. C., Robinson, S. E., Lednický, J. A., McPherson, J., Colson, S. and Bisesi Jr, J. H. (2022), "Wastewater surveillance for SARS-CoV-2 in a small coastal community: Effects of tourism on viral presence and variant identification among low prevalence populations". *Environmental research*, 208, 1-9, 112496.
- Roman, M., Roman, M., Grzegorzewska, E., Pietrzak, P. and Roman, K. (2022), "Influence of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Tourism in European Countries: Cluster Analysis Findings". *Sustainability*, 14(3), 1-17.
- Saied, A. A., Metwally, A. A. and Choudhary, O. P. (2022), "Monkeypox: An extra burden on global health". *International Journal of Surgery (London, England)*, 104, 1-15, 106745.
- Santana, G. (2004), Crisis management and tourism: Beyond the rhetoric. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 15(4), 299-321.
- Scott, N. and Laws, E. (2006). Tourism crises and disasters: Enhancing understanding of system effects. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 19(2-3), 149-158.
- Selyukh, A. (2022). How everyday Russians are feeling the impact from sanctions. available at: <https://www.npr.org/2022/03/02/1083694848/sanctions-russia-ukraine-economy-war> (accessed 05 March 2022)
- Shi, W. and Li, K. X. (2017), Impact of unexpected events on inbound tourism demand modeling: evidence of Middle East Respiratory Syndrome outbreak in South Korea". *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 22(3), 344-356.
- Sönmez, S. F., Apostolopoulos, Y. and Tarlow, P. (1999), Tourism in crisis: Managing the effects of terrorism. *Journal of Travel Research*, 38(1), 13-18.
- Tarlow, P. (2022), "Tourism tidbits: The invasion of Ukraine", available at: <https://www.hospitalitynet.org/opinion/4109134.html> (accessed 09 March 2022).
- Timmins Beth. (2022), "Ukraine's restaurants rally to the war effort", available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/business-60737248> (accessed 28 July 2022).
- The National Institute of Economic and Social Research (2022), "The Economic Costs of the Russia Ukraine Conflict". Policy Paper no. 32, 1-10.
- Turner, M. (2022), available at: <https://www.travelagentcentral.com/europe/major-hotel-groups-react-russian-invasion-ukraine> (accessed 28 July 2022).
- Türkyay, O. and Atasoy, B. (2022), "Global crises and their effects on tourism economy", Gürsoy Doğan, Sarıışık Mehmet, Robin Nunkoo ve Boğan Erhan (Edt.), *COVID-19 and the Hospitality and Tourism Industry*, Elgar Publishing, Cheltenham, 7-29.
- UNITED NATIONS, (2022), "Ukraine migration" available at: <https://www.un.org/en/> (accessed 28 July 2022).
- UNWTO, (2021), "Economic Crisis", <https://www.unwto.org/tourism-and-covid-19-unprecedented-economic-impacts>. (accessed 28 July 2022).
- UNWTO, (2022a), available at: <https://www.unwto.org/> (accessed 28 July 2022).
- UNWTO, (2022b), "Impact-Russian-offensive-in-Ukraine-on-tourism" available at: <https://www.unwto.org/impact-russian-offensive-in-ukraine-on-tourism> (accessed 28 July 2022).
- Vidal, M. D., Pozzan Paim, F., Meloni Nassar, P. and Rodrigues Simonetti, S. (2021). Impacts of Covid-19 Pandemic on Ecotourism Segment in Amazonas State, Brazil. *Anais*

- Brasileiros De Estudos Turísticos*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5770250>.
- Wachyuni, S. S. and Kusumaningrum, D. A. (2020), The effect of COVID-19 pandemic: How are the future tourist behavior. *Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*, 33(4), 67-76.
- Wong, D. and Chadwick, S. (2017), Risk and (in) security of FIFA football World Cups–outlook for Russia 2018. *Sport in society*, 20(5-6), 583-598.
- World Bank. (2020), “Air transport, passengers carried”. available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/is.air.psgc> (accessed 28 July 2022).
- Yenginar, A. (2022). Evaluation of the Grain Corridor Agreement Signed as a Result of the Russia-Ukraine War in the Framework of the Montreux Straits Convention. *Journal of Marine and Engineering Technology*, 2(2), 101-110.
- Ziyadin, S., Litvishko, O., Dubrova, M., Smagulova, G. and Suyunchaliyeva, M. (2019), Diversification tourism in the conditions of the digitalization. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 10(2), 1055-1070.

Final table. CRediT author statement

Term	Definition	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims			
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models			
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components			
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs			
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data			
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	x	x	
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools			
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse			
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	x	x	x
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post-publication stages	x	x	x
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation			
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team			
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution			
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication			

Source: reproduced from Elsevier (2022, s/p), based upon Brand et al. (2015).

Processo Editorial / Editorial Process / Proceso Editorial
Editor Chefe / Editor-in-chief / Editor Jefe: PhD Thiago D. Pimentel (UFJF).
Recebido / Received / Recibido: 29.11.2022; Revisado / Revised / Revisado: 30.12.2023 – 27.04.2023 – 28.07.2023 – 08.08.2023; Aprovado / Approved / Apobado: 28.08.2023; Publicado / Published / Publicado: 13.10.2023.
Seção revisada às cegas por pares / Double-blind peer review section / Sesión revisada por pares ciegos.